

A Novel Flavonol Glycoside from *Sageretia filiformis* Leaves

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Manuscript received 31 January 1996, revised 2 April 1996, accepted 30 April 1996

Sageretia filiformis, syn. *Rhamnus filiformis* (fam : Rhamnaceae) occurs throughout the outer Himalayas upto 6000 ft. The fruit of this plant is berry-like and becomes black when ripe¹. Several species of *Segetaria* have been reported for medicinal value². Here, we report the isolation of a novel flavonol glycoside 3-*O*-[α -L-rhamnopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucopyranosyl]-4'-methoxykaempferol from the leaves of *S. filiformis*.

Results and Discussion

Repeated column chromatography of an aqueous ethanolic extract of the defatted leaves of *S. filiformis* over silica gel and elution with chloroform-methanol afforded compound 1. It responded positive to all characteristic tests for flavonoid glycosides³. FABMS of 1 furnished peaks at m/z 777 $[M + Na]^+$ and 755 $[M + H]^+$, thus showing its molecular weight to be 754. The nature and sequence of monosaccharide units in the glycone part of 1 were revealed from the appearance of other peaks at m/z 609 $[(M + H) - 146]^+$, 463 $[(M + H) - 2 \times 146]^+$ and 301 $[(M + H) - 2 \times 146 - 162]^+$ corresponding to the sequential loss of rhamnosyl, dirhamnosyl and hexosyldirhamnosyl fragments respectively, from $[M + H]^+$ ion. These results were confirmed by acidic hydrolysis of 1 which gave an aglycone, m.p. 229°, molecular weight 300. It was characterised as 4'-methoxykaempferol by comparing its ¹H and ¹³C nmr data

with those reported in literature⁴. The neutralised and concentrated hydrolysate showed the presence of L-rhamnose and D-glucose in the ratio of 2 : 1 by photocolourimetry using light of 420 nm wavelength⁵. The points of linkage within glycone part of the molecule were confirmed by ¹³C nmr studies. Thus C-6 of inner D-glucopyranosyl unit was observed at δ 65.6 ppm, shifted upfield by ~5 ppm due to glycosidation at this point by L-rhamnopyranosyl unit. C-5 of D-glucopyranosyl unit shifted downfield as expected. C-4 of middle L-rhamnopyranosyl unit was further glycosidated by another L-rhamnopyranosyl unit as evident by downfield chemical shift δ 72.18 of this carbon (glycosidation shift ~4 ppm). The ¹³C nmr spectrum of 1 revealed the presence of 34 carbon resonances, which was in conformity with the proposed structure. Due to the presence of OCH₃ which appeared at δ 56.0, the observed chemical shifts of the *ortho*-related carbons appeared upfield rather than downfield as could be expected on glycosidation⁶. The nature of linkage at glycosidic points was found to be β for D-glucose and α for rhamnose by ¹H nmr spectral studies. The point of attachment of sugar part was confirmed to be C-3 of kaempferol by ¹³C nmr data. Thus, the chemical shifts for C-3 was observed at δ 131.0, shifted upfield by 3.5 ppm as expected. Similarly, C-2 and C-4 of kaempferol shifted downfield and observed at δ 156.7 and 177.5 respectively, as compared to kaempferol C-2 and C-4 values of δ 146.8 and 175.9 respectively⁶. All other carbon resonances of the aglycone were in agreement with that of 4'-methoxykaempferol. The exact point of linkage in the glycone part of 1 were further confirmed by preparing the permethylated product of 1 by Hakomori's method⁷. The permethylether of 1 on methanolysis followed by hydrolysis, afforded 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose. The identity of these permethylated monosaccharides was established by comparison with authentic samples on pc, available with us⁸. On the basis of the above results, compound 1 was characterised as 3-*O*-[α -L-rhamnopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucopyranosyl]-4'-methoxykaempferol.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Reichert microscope-hot stage and are uncorrected. Air-dried and powdered leaves (2 kg) of *S. filiformis* were extracted with light petroleum

(b.p. 60–80°) (4 dm³) at reflux over a steam-bath. Defatted leaves were exhaustively extracted with 85% aqueous ethanol until the extractive became colourless. The ethanolic extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure to afford a dark coloured syrupy mass (20 g). On tlc examination in CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O (65 : 32 : 10), it showed the presence of a number of prominent spots which were positive to the characteristic tests for flavonoids. The residue was repeatedly chromatographed over silica gel and eluted in the final CC with chloroform-methanol to get compound 1 (1.5 g) as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 232–34°; ¹H nmr δ (400 MHz; DMSO-d₆) δ 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-3', 5'), 6.70 (1H, s, H-8), 6.35 (1H, s, H-6), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, anomeric of glucose), 4.60 (1H, br s, anomeric of rhamnose), 4.40 (1H, br s, anomeric of other rhamnose), 1.05 (3H, s, rham-CH₃), 0.95 (3H, s, rham-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ 156.7 (C-2), 131.0 (C-3), 177.5 (C-4), 160.9 (C-5), 97.8 (C-6), 165.1 (C-7), 92.3 (C-8), 156.3 (C-9), 104.9 (C-10), 120.80 (C-1'), 133.6 (C-2'), 115.8 (C-3'), 160.0 (C-4'), 113.4 (C-5'), 133.4 (C-6'), 102.28 (C-1''), 73.5 (C-2''), 78.15 (C-3''), 71.5 (C-4''), 73.8 (C-5''), 65.6 (C-6''), 102.15 (C-18'')^a, 70.90 (C-2'')^b, 70.50 (C-3'')^c, 72.18 (C-4'')^d, 70.4 (C-5'')^e, 17.7 (C-6'')^d, 100.21 (C-1''')^a, 70.00 (C-2''')^b, 68.53 (C-3''')^c, 60.24 (C-4''')^d, 68.15 (C-5''')^e, 17.6 (C-6''')^d, 56.0 (OMe), (a, b, d values are interchangeable within molecule).

Acidic hydrolysis of 1 : Compound 1 (200 mg) was refluxed with 1 N HCl-MeOH (1 : 1, 10 ml) for 2 h over a steam-bath. Water was then added and the mixture was extracted with EtOAc. The EtOAc fraction containing the aglycone, was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as yellow needles, m.p. 229–30°. The aglycone was identified as 4'-methoxykaempferol comparison of its ¹³C nmr values with literature⁶.

The neutralised (Ag₂CO₃) aqueous hydrolysate after concentration under reduced pressure was subjected to pc using BuOH-AcOH-H₂O (5 : 1 : 4) with authentic sugars as checks. The R_f values of sugars were identical with those of glucose and rhamnose. The ratio of glucose and rhamnose was found to be 1 : 2 by photocolormetry⁴ using light of wavelength 420 nm.

Permethylation of 1 : Compound 1 (200 mg) was permethylated by Hakomori's method. NaH (400 mg) was washed with anhydrous C₆H₆ followed by washing with light petroleum and warmed with DMSO (20 ml) at 65°

over an oil-bath for 1 h with stirring under the flow of N₂. It was cooled and a solution of 1 (200 mg) in dimethylsulphoxide (4 ml) was added to it. The mixture was stirred for 1 h, CH₃I (4 ml) was added to the solution at 0–5° and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 h with stirring. After dilution with water the reaction mixture was extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml). The organic layer was washed with H₂O, sodium thiosulphate and again with H₂O and dried over Na₂SO₄. Etheral layer was concentrated and chromatographed (C₆H₆-EtOAc; 9 : 1) to afford a tlc-homogeneous permethylate of 1 (150 mg).

Methanolysis followed by hydrolysis of 1 permethylate : Compound 1 permethylate (125 mg) in dry 10% HCl-MeOH (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h over a steam-bath, the solvent was removed, H₂O (7 ml) added and the mixture further warmed on a steam-bath (3 h). It was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate on concentration under reduced pressure showed the presence of 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose (pc, n-BuOH-EtOH-H₂O; 5 : 1 : 4, authentic samples run in parallel).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to R.S.I.C., Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for spectra and to Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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